

Federal University of Santa Catarina
Department of Informatics and Statistics – INE
Course: INE5614 – Software Engineering
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Semester: 2025.2

Evaluation of a Digital System from the Perspective of Personal Data Protection

Application of guidelines from the UPC Catalogue

Introduction

The objective of this assignment is to analyse a real digital system (such as a website, application, or online platform) from the perspective of personal data protection, considering principles and rights discussed in class. The proposal aims to identify critical aspects or opportunities for improvement related to the user's interaction with this system regarding the protection of their data, using the User Privacy Communication Guidelines Catalogue (UPC Catalogue)¹ as support.

The activity must be conducted in groups of up to three students, and the final report must include the following sections.

Group identification

Provide the name and student ID of each group member here.

Description of the system selected for analysis

Provide a brief description of the system, its main features, and functionalities. Include the URL and version, if applicable.

To make the analysis, the selection, and application of guidelines from the UPC catalogue feasible, the chosen system must meet some minimum requirements:

- Web or mobile platform (mandatory).
- Provides a privacy policy (mandatory).

¹<https://psiu.inf.ufsc.br/pt-br/upcguidelines>

- Allows user profile management (mandatory).
- Allows data sharing such as comments, likes, posting photos, sharing data that belongs to other users besides the one who is sharing, etc. (desirable).

Below are some examples/suggestions of systems. The list is organised by category only to facilitate visualisation. Many of them have both web and mobile versions, and the group may choose which version to evaluate. In addition, this list is not exhaustive, and the group may choose another system to use and evaluate.

- E-commerce/marketplace platforms: Mercado Livre, Shopee, ...
- Social networks / content platforms: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, ...
- Communication and messaging applications: Telegram, Signal, ...
- Productivity and collaborative work tools: Google Drive/Docs, Zoom, Teams, ...
- Virtual assistants: Alexa, Google Assistant, Siri, ...
- Public services and utilities: Digital Work Card, e-Título, ...
- Games and virtual worlds: Roblox, Minecraft, Twitch, ...
- Educational platforms: Moodle, Coursera, ...
- Streaming and entertainment: Netflix, Spotify, Prime Video, ...

1. Application of the guidelines

The group must select at least three distinct guidelines, preferably from different groups or subgroups of the catalogue.

For each guideline, present:

1.1. Guideline identification

Provide the title and URL of the selected guideline.

1.2. Presentation of the identified problem

Present the identified problem, describing the practices related to personal data protection observed in the system that led the group to propose improvements. Include screenshots indicating the observed problems and, if applicable, provide the access link.

1.3. Justification

1.3.1. Why is the guideline appropriate for the identified problem?

Explain why the selected guideline is suitable to address the identified problem.

1.3.2. How can the guideline help solve the problem?

Explain how the guideline can contribute to solving or mitigating the problem observed in the system.

1.4. Improvement proposal based on the selected guideline

Apply, in a prototype (mockup), the implementation of how the proposed solution would look in terms of the user interface. The group may use any tool of their choice to create these mockups, such as interfaces built using HTML + CSS, Figma,² Balsamiq,³ Canva,⁴ etc.

Avoid replicating examples from the guideline. The group is encouraged to propose original solutions that align with the guideline's underlying rationale.

1.5. Connections with data protection legislation (LGPD and GDPR)

Based on the selected guidelines and the described improvement proposals, discuss how the suggested changes relate to current data protection legislation (such as the LGPD and the GDPR), considering:

- Which data subject rights are potentially better fulfilled with the proposed changes? Justify your answer.
- Are there legal principles (e.g. transparency, necessity, security, data minimisation) that are directly reflected in the selected guidelines? Justify your answer.

The purpose of this section is to reflect on how legislation serves as a basis for guiding good design and communication practices with the user, the data subject, in digital systems.

2. Conclusions

Present the group's final conclusions, considering:

- What is the group's final reflection on data protection in the scope of the selected system and on the learning achieved during the development of the assignment?
- Did the guidelines support the proposal of alternatives and/or solutions for data protection?
- Does the group consider the proposed improvement solutions to be feasible?
- Do the proposed improvements contribute to a more adequate processing of personal data in the analysed system?

²<https://figma.com>

³<https://balsamiq.com>

⁴<https://canva.com>

3. Authorisation for use of assignment results

Each group member is invited to voluntarily authorise the use of the proposals developed in this assignment using the UPC Catalogue. If you choose to authorise, you can use the *assina.ufsc.br* system to sign the statement below.

Authorisation for use of production

You are invited to authorise the use of your production, in the form of a mockup, prototype, or other visual artefact, as an example of a solution developed in the context of this research. This production may be used for academic and scientific dissemination purposes, such as in articles and in theses or dissertations, always in an anonymous way.

The production may also be used in presentations or in guidelines and best-practice catalogues, which may eventually be made publicly available.

You may choose to:

- Authorise the use of your production as an anonymous example;
 - In the case of incorporating the proposed solution as an example in the UPC catalogue, request that your name be mentioned.
- Not authorise the use of the assignment for exemplification or dissemination purposes.

Authorisation declaration

I, the undersigned, declare that:

- I have read and understood the information above.
- I have been informed that my participation is voluntary.
- I am aware that I may refuse this authorisation without any prejudice to my course evaluation.

Authorisation	Full name	Date and signature
<input type="checkbox"/> I AUTHORISE the use of the content of this assignment in an anonymous way. <input type="checkbox"/> In the case of incorporating the proposed solution as an example in the UPC catalogue, I would like my name to be cited as the author. <input type="checkbox"/> I DO NOT AUTHORISE the use of the assignment for exemplification or dissemination purposes.		
<input type="checkbox"/> I AUTHORISE the use of the content of this assignment in an anonymous way. <input type="checkbox"/> In the case of incorporating the proposed solution as an example in the UPC catalogue, I would like my name to be cited as the author. <input type="checkbox"/> I DO NOT AUTHORISE the use of the assignment for exemplification or dissemination purposes.		
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